

RESPONSE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES TO CONTACT LOADS

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ABSTRACT

Contact phenomenon observed from experiment is categorized into small and large indentation stages, which are separated by occurrence of a fiber splitting damage at the opposite side of the contact point. The applied force associated with this damage is found to be independent of the indenter sizes. In the small indentation stage where the distal side of the plate is intact, change of a laminate stacking sequences has a negligible effect on the force-indentation relationship. Also, Hertz contact law is not applicable to a thin laminate indented by a large sphere. On the other hand, fiber splitting occurs followed by delamination in the large indentation stage. The size of the delamination area is found to be proportional to contact loads and number of contact tests for loads larger than the delamination threshold.

Keywords: force-indentation, onset of damage, delamination, single and repeated loading.

1. INTRODUCTION

Response of composite laminates to contact and impact loading has raised wide attention recently because of the low strength in the thickness direction. In low velocity impact, Hertz contact law [1,2], or the modified Hertz law [3,4] has been used widely to obtain force-indentation relationship between an indenter and a laminate. Because of the complexity in obtaining the experimental force-indentation ($F - \alpha$) relationship, analytical methods have been developed to predict this contact behavior. Cairns and Lagace [5] used Bessel functions and Hertz pressure distribution to find the analytical $F - \alpha$ relationships. The laminate is assumed to be of axisymmetric properties. A similar axisymmetric assumption was used in [6] to obtain the force-indenter movement relationship. Recently, Wu and Yen [7] adopted Pagano's solution [8] and developed an exact Green's function to correlate a cross-ply laminate response to the loading applied by a rigid indenter. The $F - \alpha$ relationship and the contact pressure profile is obtained directly from iteration. However, the analytical prediction deviates from the experimental data when a laminate begins to have damage. Therefore, contact response of laminate still has to be investigated using the experimental approach, especially when damage occurs in a laminate.

Experimental results for the contact behavior were first reported by Sun and co-authors [2,3,9]. Hertz contact law or modified Hertz law was used in the loading process, and different

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relationships were used in the unloading and reloading process. However, problems of damage a laminate such as fiber splitting and delamination have not been addressed in these papers. Recently, Lagace et al. [10] explained why the stiffening effect in the indentation spring, which is the k in $F = k\alpha^n$, is due to damage of the laminate in the loading surface. This damage enlarges the contact area. As a result, the indentation spring is stiffened.

In this paper, onset of contact damage of cross-ply laminates was first studied using both experimental and analytical approaches. The contact behavior of the laminates before and after the onset of laminate damage were then discussed. In the small indentation stage where the $F - \alpha$ relationship can well be predicted using the elasticity approach in [7], the effect of changing stacking sequence, plate thickness and the indenter sizes were studied. Furthermore, force-delamination area and force-deflection relationships were investigated for laminates subjected to both single and repeated loading.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Laminates used in this study were made of Toho Q-1112 graphite/epoxy prepregs. The stacking sequences used were $(0_n^\circ/90_n^\circ)_s$, $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_{ns}$, $(0_m^\circ/45_m^\circ/90_m^\circ/-45_m^\circ)_s$ and $(0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ)_{ms}$. The thicknesses are 1.0 mm, 2.0 mm and 4.0 mm. The indentors were made of hard steel spheres of Rc60. The diameters of the indentors are 12.7 mm, 19.1 mm and 25.0 mm. More than 100 test runs were performed.

The material properties of the composites are:

$$E_1 = 148GPa, \quad S_1 = 1989MPa, \quad \epsilon_{1t} = 1.35 \quad (1)$$

$$E_2 = 10.0GPa, \quad S_2 = 32.6MPa, \quad \epsilon_{2t} = 0.33 \quad (2)$$

$$G_{12} = 4.74GPa, \quad S_{12} = 72.0MPa \quad \nu_{12} = 0.31 \quad (3)$$

where 1 and 2 are parallel and perpendicular to the fiber direction, respectively. E , G , ν and ϵ_t are the Young's modulus, shear modulus Poisson's ratio and ultimate tensile strain, respectively.

An Instron 8000 universal test machine was employed for contact test. The test set-up is similar to that in Tan and Sun [2]. The stroke speed used is 0.01 mm/sec. The applied contact force was recorded very 0.05 mm stroke movement. The indentation value was measured using a LVDT (Linear Variable Differential Transformer) which can accurately measure a displacement of 0.001 mm. End-tabs were mounted on the edges of all the $138mm \times 138mm$ laminates to prevent the specimens from sliding during the test. The specimen was clamped on all four edges and with $100mm \times 100mm$ spans in the contact test. Kyowa KFC-2-350-C1-11 strain gauges were mounted on the laminates, as shown in Figure 1.

$(0_4^\circ/90_4^\circ)_s$ laminates indented by a 12.7 mm diameter sphere were tested extensively in this study, and were used as a reference to study the effect of changing laminate thickness and stacking sequence, and indenter size on the contact response. The averaged ultimate contact load for this test configuration is $F_u = 2.82 kN$.

3. ONSET OF CONTACT DAMAGE

A typical force-indentation relationship for a $(0_8^\circ/90_8^\circ)_s$ laminate contacted by a 25 mm diameter indenter is illustrated in Figure 2. As the applied force increases, there is a "bip" sound clearly heard during the test. The corresponding indentation values are $53.5 \mu m$. This "bip" sound was heard in all the test runs in this study. Also, there is a jump found in the $F - \alpha$ curve in Figure 2. Apparently, the laminate is damaged. The indentation corresponding

to this "bip" sound is defined as the critical indentation, α_c . Table 1 lists α_c values for all the test configurations. To find what is the cause to this noise during a contact test, 20%, i.e., $F = 0.56 kN$, of the ultimate contact load of $(0_4^0/90_4^0)_s$ laminates was applied to a $(0_4^0/90_4^0)_s$ laminate by a 12.7 mm indenter. This load corresponds to indentation of $\alpha = 57 \mu m$ and is larger than $\alpha_c = 39.0 \mu m$, as listed in Table 1. The specimen was then X-rayed. The result from the X-ray picture shows that there is only a fiber splitting crack on the distal side of the specimen right underneath the initial contact point in the third layer of the laminate, but neither delamination nor matrix crack was observed. Therefore, the fiber splitting crack is the first damage mechanism for laminates of these configurations indented by a rigid sphere. This damage mode was also observed in [11] for laminates subject to low velocity impact.

As shown in Figure 2, the $F - \alpha$ data are not continuous at $\alpha = \alpha_c$. Thus, if one fits the test data including those beyond $\alpha = \alpha_c$ rather than only use the data with $\alpha \leq \alpha_c$, the indentation spring, k , will be stiffer. This is because of the occurrence of the fiber splitting damage that results in a "hinged" line in the laminate when it is indented by a sphere. With this "hinge" line, the plate is easier to conform to the rigid sphere. Consequently, more contact force is needed to produce the same indentation.

Table 1 also lists the contact loads corresponding to the onset of fiber splitting damage. It is found that these contact loads seem to independent to the indenter sizes when the laminate thickness is fixed, i.e., $\approx 0.82, 0.27$ and $0.14 kN$ for 4, 2 and 1mm thick plates, respectively. Because the indenter size affects the contact area, an analysis which can accurately calculate both the contact pressure distribution on a laminate and the strain field inside the laminate in the contact region is needed.

The analytical method employed in this study is the same as the one in [7], which has successfully predicted the $F - \alpha$ relationship of a laminated plate indented by a rigid sphere. Because the fiber splitting damage is in the fiber direction, the strain perpendicular to it is of the most interest. Figure 3 depicts the predicted strain, ϵ_{yy} , underneath the initial contact point along the thickness in a 4 mm $(0_8^0/90_8^0)_s$ laminate. The contact load is 0.82 kN. This is the load that causes the onset of fiber splitting damage of the 4 mm thick laminates, as listed in Table 1. The indentors used are 12.7 mm, 19.1 mm, 25.0 mm, 50.0 mm and 100 mm in diameters. The result shows an essentially identical strain magnitude on the distal side of the plate. Therefore, the onset of the initial damage of the laminates is independent of the indenter sizes. However, the contact area calculated using this method ranges from 0.80 mm^2 to 4.64 mm^2 for indenter diameters of 12.7 mm and 100 mm, respectively. Further, use different indentors affects only the ϵ_{yy} distribution in the first layer of the laminate.

4. SMALL INDENTATION

4.1. Change of Laminate Stacking Sequence

Because the fiber splitting damage has not occurred in the small indentation stage, the $F - \alpha$ curve is continuous. In Figure 4, 2.0 mm thick laminates of four different stacking sequences show essentially the same $F - \alpha$ relationships for indentation smaller than 39.0 μm , which is the onset of laminate damage for $(0_4^0/90_4^0)_s$ laminates. Thus, the same 1.5 power law of Hertz can be used to predict the $F - \alpha$ relationships regardless of the stacking sequence change.

4.2. Change of Indenter Size

In Hertz contact law, the force-indentation relationship is proportional to the square root of the indenter diameter. Although this relationship is only valid for two isotropic, elastic

bodies with quadratic profiles in contact with each other, this relationship has been widely applied to laminates indented by rigid spheres. For example, the modified Hertz Law proposed in [3,9] has the form of

$$F = (\sqrt{8}/3)\sqrt{D} \left[\frac{1 - \nu_s^2}{E} + \frac{1}{E_3} \right]^{-1} \alpha^{3/2} \quad (4)$$

where D , ν and E are the diameter, Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus of the indenter, and E_3 is the Young's modulus of the plate in the thickness direction. To evaluate the validity of this $F - \sqrt{D}$ relationship, both $(0_4^{\circ}/90_4^{\circ})_s$ and $(0_8^{\circ}/90_8^{\circ})_s$ laminates were indented by indentors of 12.7 mm, 19.1 mm and 25.0 mm diameters. The tested $F - \alpha$ relationship is best fitted using the relationship of $F = k\alpha^{1.5}$ for indentation in the small indentation stage. The results are listed in Table 2. k/\bar{k} in the 4th and the 7th columns are the normalized stiffness of the indentation spring, which is determined by dividing the k value by that with the indenter of 12.7 mm in diameter. The deviation between the k/\bar{k} and the ratio of $\sqrt{D/\bar{D}}$ is listed in columns 5 and 8, where $\bar{D} = 12.7mm$. The more deviation found for the $(0_4^{\circ}/90_4^{\circ})_s$ plates is because it is thinner than the $(0_8^{\circ}/90_8^{\circ})_s$ laminates. Thus, the former deviate more from a half space. Also, the difference of using the 25 mm indenter is 13.6% and 8.6%, which is larger than 4.1% and 1.6 %, respectively, for the case involving the 19.1 mm indenter. This is because the 25.0 mm indenter causes larger contact area. For a plate of a finite thickness, a larger contact area means a smaller ratio of the plate thickness to the contact diameter. Thus, it deviates more from a half space solution. Consequently, the $F - \sqrt{D}$ relationship will no more be valid for a thin laminates indented by a large indenter.

4.3. Change of Laminate Thickness

Effect of laminate thickness change on the $F - \alpha$ relationship is illustrated in Figure 5 for cross-ply laminates of 1.0 mm, 2.0 mm and 4.0 mm in thickness, which were subject to indentation by a 25 mm diameter indenter. These were the most extreme cases in the test runs because the 25 mm diameter indenter gave the smallest ratio of plate thickness to contact area for the same indentation. Thus, results obtained from these tests are expected to deviate most seriously from the half space solution.

In the beginning, the difference among these three curves is insignificant. Thus, the effect of changing laminate thickness is negligible. At $\alpha \approx 16.5\mu m$, which is the α_c for laminates of 1.0 mm in thickness (Table 1), the $F - \alpha$ curve for this thinnest plate first deviates from the rest two curves. As the contact force keeps increasing, the deviation between the 2.0 mm and 4.0 mm thick plates becomes more significant. The 2.0 mm thick laminate shows a stiffer $F - \alpha$ relationship due to its greater flexibility than the 4.0 mm thick laminate. This greater flexibility results in a larger contact area. Thus, it requires a larger loading to acquire the same indentation. When α goes beyond $\alpha_c = 27 \mu m$ for the $(0_4^{\circ}/90_4^{\circ})_s$ laminates, jumps start to occur in the $F - \alpha$ curve for this 2.0 mm thick plate. The small indentation stage ended because a fiber splitting crack occurs.

5. LARGE INDENTATION

It has been found from the previous section that fiber splitting cracking is the first damage mechanism in the contact test. In this section, $(0_4^{\circ}/90_4^{\circ})_s$ specimens are loaded at 20%, 40%, 50%, 60%, 70 % and 80% of the ultimate contact strength of $F_u = 2.82 kN$ to find the force-delamination area relationship. X-ray pictures were taken for each specimens. The contact force and delamination area relationship is shown in Figure 6. A straight line is found to fit the force-delamination area relationship. It is also found from this figure that the delamination

threshold is approximately 27% of the ultimate contact strength of the laminates.

To detect the onset of delamination damage, strain gauges were also mounted at locations #2 on both front and distal sides of a $(0_4^{\circ}/90_4^{\circ})_s$ laminate. The strain values are shown in Figure 7. In the beginning of the contact test where there is no delamination failure occurs, the two strains are symmetric about the zero strain axis, indicating a pure bending mechanism. However, at $F \approx 0.7kN$, approximating 25% of F_u , abrupt change of strain history was observed, indicating that the delamination crack front passes through this location. After that the two strain curves has no correlation because the laminate is separated at this location. The deviation of delamination threshold obtained from Figures 6 and 7 are considered tolerable. Therefore, the delamination threshold can either be obtained from a linear regression analysis of the force-delamination data, or detected by using strain gauges.

6. REPEATED CONTACT

60% of the ultimate contact strength were acted on a 2 mm thick $(0_4^{\circ}/90_4^{\circ})_s$ laminates to study the effect of repeated contact loading on the delamination propagation inside the cross-ply laminates. Figure 8 depicts this relationship. A linear relationship is found when the number of contact test is less than six. After that the delamination area is not much extended because of the constraint of the four fixed-end boundary. Thus, if the span of a plate is large enough, the delamination area is believed to extend proportional to the number of impact test.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Experimental results for the contact phenomena of laminates indented by rigid spheres have been presented in this paper. It has been found that fiber splitting is the first laminate damage mechanism for $(0_m^{\circ}/90_m^{\circ})_s$ laminates, which can be clearly detected by listening to the damage noise during test. This damage is found to be independent of the sizes of the indentors.

In the small indentation stage, where fiber splitting damage has not occurred, change of the stacking sequences of a laminate has an insignificant effect on the $F - \alpha$ relationship. However, the Hertz prediction, which has a linear relationship of $F - \sqrt{D}$ and was derived essentially based on a half space condition, is found to be inappropriate for a thin plate indented by a large indenter. On the other hand, in the large indentation stage, the delamination area is proportional to the applied contact load when it is larger than the threshold. This threshold can be detected either by the force and delamination area relationship, or by abrupt change of the strain gauge signals. Further, the location which a delamination crack front or a fiber splitting crack front passes through can be detected using strain gauges. It is also found that the delamination area is proportional to the number of contact times.

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Laminate thickness(mm)	Indenter diameter (mm)		
	25.0	19.1	12.7
h	α_c/F	α_c/F	α_c/F
4.0	53.5 / 0.82	66.0 / 0.82	86.5 / 1.10
2.0	27.0 / 0.27	31.5 / 0.27	39.0 / 0.28
1.0	16.5 / 0.15	17.5 / 0.14	18.5 / 0.10

unit: $\mu\text{m}/\text{kN}$

Table 1 Indentations and Associated Contact Forces for $(0_n^\circ/90_n^\circ)$, Laminates, $n = 2, 4$ and 8 .

Figure 5 Effect of Changing Laminate Thickness on $F - \alpha$ Relationships.

Figure 7 Strain History for $(0_4^2/90_4^2)_s$ Laminate by 50% of the Ultimate Contact Load.

Figure 6 Contact Force and Delamination Area Relationship, $D = 12.7mm$.

Figure 8 Delamination Area and Number of Contact Relationship for $(0_4^2/90_4^2)_s$ Laminate by $0.6F_u$, $F_u = 2.82kN$.